

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish & Wildlife Office
650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300
Sacramento, California 95814-4700

In reply refer to:
08FBDT00-2020-F-0020

November 10, 2020

Ms. Frances Malamud-Roam
Senior Regulatory Project Manager
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
450 Golden Gate Ave., 4th floor
San Francisco, CA 94102

Subject: Formal Consultation on the Bayfront Canal and Atherton Channel Flood Management and Restoration Project, Cities of Redwood City and Menlo Park, San Mateo County, California (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers File Number: 2018-00161S)

Dear Ms. Malamud-Roam:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps') October 25, 2019, letter requesting initiation of informal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) for the Bayfront Canal and Atherton Channel Flood Management and Restoration Project (project) in the Cities of Redwood City and Menlo Park in San Mateo County, California. Your request was received by the Service on October 28, 2019. At issue are the proposed project's effects to the endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*), endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*)¹, endangered California least tern (*Sterna antillarum browni*) and the threatened western snowy plover (*Charadrius nivosus nivosus*). This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR § 402).

The Federal action on which we are consulting is the Corps' issuance of a permit under Section 404 of the Clean Water Act of 1972, as amended (33 U.S.C. § 1344 *et seq.*), and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899, as amended (33 U.S.C. § 403 *et seq.*), to implement the project in the Bayfront Canal and Flood Slough. Pursuant to 50 CFR § 402.12(j), you submitted a biological assessment for our review and requested concurrence with the findings presented therein.

¹ Until the Service officially adopts recent nomenclature changes made by the American Ornithologists' Union to Ridgway's Rail (*Rallus obsoletus*), we maintain the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) in this correspondence. Note, the change in taxonomic assignment does not change the listing status of the species.

In considering your request, we have based our evaluation on the following: (1) the Corps' October 25, 2019, letter requesting informal consultation with enclosed biological assessment dated May 2019; (2) the revised April 2020 biological assessment; (3) electronic mail (email) correspondence between the Service, the Corps, and the project consultants; and (4) other information available to the Service.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the California least tern. The closest known breeding site for this species is located approximately 8 miles northeast of the Action Area. The Pond S5 Forebay does not currently provide suitable foraging habitat for this species, as it is seasonally dry and hydrologically separated from San Francisco Bay. Flood Slough provides potential foraging habitat for this species. Levees in the Action Area provide nominally suitable breeding habitat for this species, but the high level of human presence makes use of these habitats by the tern unlikely. Pile driving is anticipated to occur outside the California least tern breeding season. Implementation of Conservation Measures BIO-7 (Protection of California Least Tern), BIO-3 (Protection of Nesting Birds), and GEN-4 (General Site Disturbance Restrictions) (mentioned below in the *Description of the Proposed Action*) may minimize the potential for construction-related adverse effects on California least tern in the unlikely event they forage or nest within the Action Area. Reinitiation of this consultation may be required if California least tern nest in the project area. Regarding operations, California least terns are typically present in the San Francisco Bay area between April and August and would therefore be absent during periods when the box culverts would be discharging wet season high flows into the S5 Forebay.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the western snowy plover. Western snowy plover is not known to occur in the Action Area but is known to nest at Ravenswood Pond R5 approximately 200 feet northeast of the Action Area. Although a noise analysis was not conducted, construction-related noise is not anticipated to exceed ambient conditions at Ravenswood Pond R5. Pile driving is anticipated to occur outside the western snowy plover breeding season. Implementation of Conservation Measures BIO-6 (Protection of Western Snowy Plover), BIO-3 (Protection of Nesting Birds), Measure GEN-4 (General Site Disturbance Restrictions) may minimize the potential for construction-related adverse effects on western snowy plover in the unlikely event they nest within the Action Area, but reinitiation of this consultation may be required.

The Service does not concur with the Corps' determination that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail due to potential effects to individuals from noise disturbance, habitat modification, and the implementation of certain *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the remainder of this document is the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail. No critical habitat has been designated for these species, therefore no critical habitat for listed species will be affected by the proposed project.

Consultation History

February 1, 2019	The Service received a request for consultation on the project from the Corps.
February 26, 2019	The Corps withdrew their February 1, 2019 request for consultation via email.
October 28, 2019	The Service received the current request for consultation on the project.
December 19, 2019	The Service participated in a site visit. The Service recommended formal consultation and requested revisions to the biological assessment to add information regarding the berm lowering and passive revegetation, and to revise impacts to and conservation measures for the salt marsh harvest mouse.
February 2, 2020	The project consultant discussed positive results of California clapper rail surveys in Flood Slough with the Service. The Service presented options for the construction process to proceed during the rail breeding season including: (1) initiating construction prior to the breeding season and having construction continue non-stop during the breeding season (allowing for delays no greater than a weekend); or (2) installation of sound attenuation blankets on temporary fencing placed along the periphery of Flood Slough adjacent to areas of active construction.
April 22, 2020	The Service received a revised biological assessment dated April 2020 via email from the consultant.
July 2020	The Service, Corps, and consultant exchanged emails regarding project effects.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The proposed project includes construction of a lateral weir diversion structure alongside Bayfront Canal, two parallel underground box culverts between the Bayfront Canal and the South Bay Salt Ponds (SBSP) Restoration Pond S5 Forebay, an outlet into the Pond S5 Forebay with head wall, wing walls, and riprap for energy dissipation and maintenance and operation. It also includes Bedwell Bayfront Park entry improvements and onsite restoration.

Lateral Weir Diversion Structure

A 60-foot long concrete lateral weir diversion structure would be constructed along the south bank of the Bayfront Canal, just upstream of the Bayfront Canal tide gates. The weir would have a crest height at approximately 3.75 feet North American Vertical Datum (NAVD), which would

be 4.75 feet above the Bayfront Canal thalweg (-1.0 feet NAVD), allowing higher flood flows in Bayfront Canal to overtop the weir and enter an approximately 14-foot deep entrance chamber to the box culverts. Stormwater flows less than 4.75 feet deep in the Bayfront Canal would continue to exit into Flood Slough and ultimately San Francisco Bay via existing tide gates.

The overall dimensions of the diversion structure would be approximately 24 feet wide by 80 feet long. The entrance chamber would be covered by a trash rack to prevent trash from entering the box culverts and the connected SBSP Restoration ponds. A service grate would also be installed above the entrance chamber for maintenance access into the chamber and culverts. The diversion structure would also include a two-horsepower manually-operated sump pump connected to a 4-inch drain line that would outlet into Flood Slough through the existing tide gates concrete headwall. The sump pump and drain line would be used to remove any standing water in the box culverts during the dry season and when otherwise necessary for inspection or maintenance of the culverts.

Approximately 145 cubic yards of rock would be installed adjacent to the diversion structure on the south bank of the Bayfront Canal to prevent scour and erosion of the bank where water flows into the diversion structure.

Box Culverts

A total of two 8-foot wide by 5-foot tall box culverts would be installed in parallel underground, connecting the lateral weir diversion structure with the outlet into the SBSP Restoration Pond S5 Forebay. Each box culvert would be approximately 540 feet long. The box culverts would follow the existing alignment of a series of salt production brine conveyance channels, which would be filled in following trenching and installation of the culverts. The bottom elevations of the box culverts would range from -8 NAVD at the diversion structure to 0 NAVD at the SBSP Restoration Pond S5 Forebay outlet. Manhole access shafts above each box culvert would be installed approximately 225 feet west of the Forebay outlet.

Outlet Structure

A concrete outlet structure (i.e., headwall) would be constructed at the outfall into an existing brine conveyance channel adjacent to the SBSP Restoration Pond S5 Forebay. The brine channel would be recontoured to connect to the Forebay adjacent to the outlet structure. The outlet structure would be fitted with two flap-gates, one per box culvert. The flap-gates would prevent water from reversing course back into the culverts following high flow events. Approximately 90 cubic yards of rock would be installed adjacent to the outfall structure to dissipate flows entering the Forebay. The dimensions of the rock apron would be approximately 25 feet by 40 feet.

Flood waters entering the SBSP Restoration Pond S5 Forebay would mix with tidal inflows via water control structures at three different locations in the Ravenswood Pond Complex (installed as part SBSP Restoration), ultimately flowing into San Francisco Bay. This process and the management of water control structures are discussed in more detail in Project Operations and Maintenance, below.

Forebay Excavation

Two feet of soil on average would be excavated from the SBSP Restoration Pond S5 Forebay (approximately 4.2 acres in size) to increase its flood storage capacity. This would generate approximately 20,328 cubic yards of excavated materials that would be beneficially reused by the adjacent SBSP Restoration of the Ravenswood Pond Complex in upland transition zone areas, on nesting islands, or to raise the bottom of Pond R4. The side-slopes of the recontoured Forebay would be seeded with a native species seed mix comparable to that used in transitional zones for the SBSP Restoration.

Berm Lowering and Onsite Restoration

An existing berm next to the SBSP Restoration Pond S5 Forebay would be recontoured and lowered in order to expand onsite vegetated salt marsh along the periphery of the Forebay. This existing berm was originally constructed to separate the brine conveyance channel from the SBSP Restoration Pond S5 Forebay. The existing berm consists of unconsolidated fill and does not serve a flood control purpose; it supports predominantly non-native grassland and ruderal species with salt marsh pickleweed along the toe of its slope. The top two feet (approximate) of the berm would be removed to bring the soil level down to the elevation where the pickleweed is thriving. This grading would occur in conjunction with the proposed excavation of the SBSP Restoration Pond S5 Forebay. The finished grade would create a 10-foot to 15-foot wide by approximately 840-foot long strip that would become subject to more frequent inundation after the SBSP connection to Flood Slough is completed. Following grading, salt marsh pickleweed would establish passively on the lowered berm. Restoration would create 0.28 acre of salt marsh habitat. In addition, approximately 0.069 acre of the berm would be removed to allow connection of the proposed outlet with the Forebay, increasing the extent of open water at the project site.

Post-Construction Site Restoration and Entry Improvements

Following the installation of the box culverts, temporarily disturbed areas used during construction would be restored to approximate preconstruction conditions except that the impacted brine conveyance channels would be permanently filled and compacted to match the existing grades of the adjacent Bedwell Bayfront Park entrance road and adjoining access roads. Decomposed granite would be placed around the diversion structure for maintenance truck access. Newly graded slopes would be hydroseeded with non-invasive landscape and/or native plant species. All construction materials and debris would be removed from the project site and recycled or otherwise disposed of off-site. The impacted portion of Marsh Road and any other damaged paved parking adjoining the road would be repaved.

Implementation of Bedwell Bayfront Park Entry Improvements by the City of Menlo Park would follow post-construction clean-up for the box culverts. Park entry improvements would include the following:

- Gateway Sign – A new park entry sign at the Marsh Road and Bayfront Expressway intersection to clearly identify the park name and increase visibility from all directions of travel.
- Entry Plaza – A new pedestrian entry plaza including an Americans with Disabilities Act-

compliant curb ramp that will connect planned pedestrian sidewalk improvements along Haven Avenue and Marsh Road with the Park entry trails and an existing segment of the Bay Trail paralleling the Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge (Refuge).

- Trail Improvements – An existing pedestrian and bicycle multi-use path, designated as Bay Trail and connecting a segment of Bay Trail along Bayfront Expressway with the portion of Bay Trail around the perimeter of Bedwell Bayfront Park, would be reconstructed. The reconstruction would increase pedestrian and bicycle safety by separating the trail from vehicular traffic, which currently is co-mingled along the entrance road. Additionally, the existing dirt path next to the box culvert outlet would be improved.
- Entrance Road – The entrance road would be reconstructed to incorporate a vehicle roundabout, new automatic park entrance gates, and green infrastructure improvements, where feasible. The reconstruction of the entrance roadway would incorporate an increase in the finished road grade elevations to approximately 2-feet above the designated base flood elevation to combat tidal flooding and provide resiliency to future sea level rise.

Park entry improvements would occur within the existing Marsh Road and road shoulder, existing paths, and disturbed upland areas used for construction of the bypass culverts.

Construction Methods

The lateral weir diversion structure, outlet structure, and culvert manhole access shafts would all be formed and cast-in-place concrete facilities. The box culverts would be pre-fabricated and installed using open trench construction. Trench excavation depths for the box culverts would vary between 15 and 24 feet, allowing for approximately 4 feet of pipe bedding material underneath the culverts.

All underground utilities would be protected in place using temporary support systems or anchoring to the ground above, including the California Department of Transportation (Caltrans) storm drain culverts (two 48-inch reinforced concrete pipes) and Cargill's transbay pipeline that runs along the existing brine conveyance channels.

Project construction would consist of the following phases:

- Phase 1 – Mobilize and Install Lateral Weir Diversion Structure
- Phase 2 – Construct Outfall Structure and Grade Brine Channel Berm and Pond S5 Forebay
- Phase 3 – Install Box Culverts Between Diversion Structure and Marsh Road
- Phase 4 – Install Box Culverts Between Marsh Road and Outlet Structure
- Phase 5 – Install Box Culverts Under Marsh Road
- Phase 6 – Complete Finish Grading and Site Restoration/Landscaping
- Phase 7 – Complete Park Entry Improvements
- Phase 8 – Complete Final Punch List Items

Phasing the installation of the box culverts would allow access to Bedwell Bayfront Park and to the West Bay Sanitary District facilities to be maintained throughout construction via the

existing Marsh Road entrance or a temporary detour around construction at the site.

Dewatering

It is anticipated that dewatering would be required during construction due to the project location along the shoreline. An assessment of subsurface water migration and rates would be made during initial construction excavation to determine the level of groundwater control and dewatering required. Dewatering systems used during construction may include sump pumps, a well point system, or localized ground freezing depending on field conditions at the time of construction.

Dewatering activities would be conducted in accordance with all existing regulations and requirements. If sump pumps or a well point system were utilized, then a sediment containment basin would be needed. A temporary sediment basin would be constructed within the SBSP Restoration Pond S5 Forebay. Alternatively, a Baker tank would be used if needed to meet receiving water quality objectives prior to discharge back into Flood Slough.

Diversion Structure Isolation

Sheet piles would be installed along the lower bank of the Bayfront Canal next to the lateral weir diversion structure work area in order to isolate the construction work area from the canal. The sheet piles would prevent flow from entering into the work area. The sheet piles would be supplemented with clean gravel bags placed along the top of bank to fill gaps or to extend the exclusion barrier preventing flow from entering the work area. The sheet piles would be installed using either a vibratory pile driver or impact hammer attachment on an excavator.

Construction Staging

Two primary construction staging areas would be established, one on either side of the Marsh Road entrance to Bedwell Bayfront Park. Construction staging would include the following elements:

- An office trailer;
- One or two Conex storage containers;
- A material storage area;
- A graveled employee parking area;
- A fuel storage truck;
- A Baker tank for dewatering (if needed);
- Space for equipment storage;
- Portable restrooms;
- Perimeter fencing; and
- Security lights (optional).

Excavated material would be stockpiled in staging areas. The SBSP Restoration Pond S5 Forebay would also be used for temporary materials storage prior to excavation to the finish design depth.

Construction Equipment

The main pieces of equipment that may be used during construction of the Proposed Project are the following:

- Long-reach excavator
- Front-end loader
- Bulldozer
- Plate compactor
- Crawler crane
- Flat-bed delivery truck
- Concrete truck
- Dump truck
- Water truck
- Vibratory roller
- Asphalt paver
- Vibratory driver
- Impact driver
- Diesel generator

Chemical Use and Storage

Hazardous materials would be stored in designated areas at staging areas, away from drainage areas and ignition hazards, such as electrical outlets or overhead hazards. Lubricants may be stored in 55-gallon drums. Fuels would remain stored and transported on mobile 500-gallon refuelers used to refuel equipment. Secondary containment would be provided for storage tanks containing 55 gallons or more, such as spill trays, lined basins or double-walled tanks, or other containment devices.

Timing of Work

Construction is expected to take 12 months (see Table 1).

Table 1. Proposed Construction Timetable

TASK	DURATION	START	END
Bidding		10/15/20	12/15/20
Bid award		12/15/20	12/15/20
Construction		1/4/21	12/15/21
Mobilization	1 week	1/4/21	1/11/21
Construct lateral weir diversion structure, outfall structure, and grade brine ditch berm and Forebay	3 months	1/12/21	4/6/21
Install box culverts between diversion structure and Marsh Road	2 months	4/7/21	6/7/21

Install box culverts between Marsh Road and outlet structure	3 months	6/8/21	9/8/21
Install box culverts under Marsh Road	2 months	9/9/21	11/9/21
Complete grading, landscaping, and final punch list items	1 months	11/10/21	12/15/21

Project Operations and Maintenance

Project operations and maintenance activities would be conducted in coordination with the Refuge. Flood waters entering the SBSP Restoration Pond S5 Forebay would mix with tidal inflows via the Ravenswood Pond Complex water control structures installed as part SBSP Restoration, ultimately flowing into San Francisco Bay.

It is anticipated that the Refuge will not open the new SBSP Restoration water control structures in Ponds R5 and S5 until this project is installed.

Flood Management Operations

Operations and maintenance of water levels in the combined Ponds R5, S5, and the S5 Forebay following completion of the proposed project and the SBSP Phase 2 restoration would be managed as follows:

- The water levels in Ponds R5, S5, and the S5 Forebay would be actively managed year-round by opening and closing the SBSP water control structures as needed to maintain desired surface elevations, flows, and water quality. Refuge staff would operate the SBSP water control structures and provide maintenance and cleaning of them as needed.
 - Summer and Fall Configuration – The SBSP water control structures connecting Ponds R5, S5 and the S5 Forebay with Pond R4 and Flood Slough would typically remain fully open allowing maximum tidal water exchange through the water control structures.

During this period, the Bayfront Canal box culverts would be drained of any standing water.

- Winter and Spring Configuration – The SBSP water control structures connecting Ponds R5, S5 and the S5 Forebay with Pond R4 and Flood Slough would be partially closed during the storm season (one culvert pipe would be fully open allowing tidal exchange and one culvert pipe would be set to allow tidal flows out of the ponds but not into the ponds). This partial closure to incoming tidal flows would result in lower water levels within Ponds R5, S5, and the S5 Forebay in order to maximize flood water storage for bypassed flood flows through the box culverts from Bayfront Canal during the storm season.

During this period, the Bayfront Canal culvert gates would remain open, allowing the transfer of flood flows into the Pond S5 Forebay throughout the storm season. Stormwater flows would typically only enter the Forebay during high tide cycles

when Bayfront Canal flood flows back up at the Flood Slough tide gates. At the same time that flood flows enter the Forebay through the box culverts, high tide flows would also enter the Forebay via the SBSP Flood Slough water control structure, which would mix with the incoming freshwater flood flows.

Storm flood flows that enter Bayfront Canal during low tide periods would typically enter Flood Slough through the existing tide gates. Any flooding that backs up at the Flood Slough tide gates during low tide would also enter the Forebay via the box culverts. This flood flow would rapidly exit the Forebay into Flood Slough via the SBSP water control structures.

The start and end dates for the Winter/Spring configuration would vary depending on the anticipated start and end of the storm season.

Culvert Maintenance

Periodic maintenance of the box culverts would be required following construction. Maintenance would require a staff person to travel to the project site one or two times a month to inspect the site, remove trash and debris from the trash rack and sump pump, check the operation and structural integrity of the diversion structure and culvert gates, and address any vandalism repairs to the facility. Sediment would also be removed from the outfall structure as needed. The flap gates would be lubricated and exercised for proper operation. Maintenance of the box culverts is not expected as they are designed to be self-cleaning. During the rainy season, the frequency of maintenance inspections would be increased as necessary in response to storm events. The Refuge would be responsible for ongoing levee and pond maintenance in the Forebay as part of the operations and maintenance activities associated with the SBSP Restoration Project and separate permit requirements.

Onsite Restoration Monitoring

Salt marsh vegetation is anticipated to develop on the top of the lowered berm in the Forebay. Vegetation establishment in this area will be monitored annually for up to three years following the completion of construction. Monitoring will include visual estimates of plant cover and composition along with ground-based photo-monitoring at two monumented permanent photo stations. If invasive plant species are found to impede the passive establishment of native vegetation in this area, these invasive species will be removed by hand or using hand tools if appropriate. It is anticipated that the tidal connection between the Forebay and Flood Slough will be completed and opened sometime during the monitoring period, which will further enhance establishment of salt marsh vegetation on the berm.

Performance criteria for vegetative cover for the berm lowering area wetlands are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Performance Criteria for Onsite Restoration Area

Year after Opening of Construction	Vegetative Cover by Native Species (percent cover)
1	10
2	25
3	40

Conservation Measures

General and species specific conservation measures are presented below in Table 3.

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
<i>Construction, Erosion Control and Flood Risk Management</i>	
GEN-1. Vehicular/Equipment Operation and Maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Vehicles driving on levees to access the Bay, tidal sloughs, or channels for construction or monitoring activities would travel at speeds slow enough to minimize noise and dust disturbance. b. Proper equipment maintenance and fueling procedures will ensure that no fluids are discharged into streams, water bodies, or wetlands, and that any spills are promptly cleaned up, reported (if necessary), and properly disposed of. c. A separate area will be designated for equipment maintenance and fueling, away from any slopes, streams, water bodies, wetlands, or drainage facilities. Fuel absorbent mats will be used when refueling equipment. Where feasible, vehicle cleaning, maintenance, refueling, and fuel storage will be 150 feet or more from any stream, water body, or wetland. d. Where equipment is expected to be stored for more than a few days, cleanup materials and tools will be kept nearby and available for immediate use. Equipment will not be stored in areas that will potentially drain to watercourses or drainage facilities. If equipment must be stored in areas with the potential to generate runoff, drip pans, berms, sandbags, or absorbent booms should be employed to contain any leaks or spills. e. No more than 4,000 gallons of fuel will be transported at any one time on the project site. f. All equipment will be maintained free of petroleum leaks.

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
	All vehicles operated at the project site will be inspected daily for leaks and, if necessary, repaired before leaving the staging area. Inspections will be documented in a record that is available for review on request.
GEN-2. Work Area Maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Berm and cover stockpiles of sand, dirt or other construction material with tarps when rain is forecast or if not actively being used within 14 days. b. Designate an area fitted with appropriate Best Management Practices (BMPs) for vehicle and equipment parking and storage. c. Perform major maintenance, repair jobs, and vehicle and equipment washing off-site. d. If vehicle maintenance must be done onsite, work away from storm drains and over a drip pan big enough to collect fluids. e. Recycle or dispose of fluids as hazardous waste. f. No vehicle or equipment cleaning will be done onsite.
GEN-3. Spill Prevention and Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. The construction Contractor will be required to develop and submit a Spill Prevention and Response Plan for approval by the County. b. Equipment and materials for cleanup of spills will be available on site and spills and leaks will be cleaned up immediately and disposed of according to guidelines stated in the Spill Prevention and Response Plan. c. Spill response kits will always be in close proximity when using hazardous materials (e.g., at crew trucks and other logical locations). All field personnel will be advised of these locations. d. Absorbent materials will be maintained at the project site in sufficient quantity to effectively immobilize the volume of petroleum-based fluids contained in the largest tank present at the site. Acceptable absorbent materials are those that are manufactured specifically for the containment and clean-up of hazardous materials. e. County staff will routinely inspect the work site to verify that spill prevention and response measures are properly implemented and maintained. f. For small spills on impervious surfaces, absorbent materials will be used to remove the spill, rather than hosing it down with water. For small spills on pervious surfaces such as soil, the spill will be excavated and properly disposed of rather than buried. Absorbent materials will be collected and disposed of properly and promptly.

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> g. Containers for storage, transportation, and disposal of contaminated absorbent materials will be provided on the project site. Petroleum products and contaminated soil will be disposed of according to Federal, State, and local regulations. h. In the event of a contaminant spill, work at the project site will immediately cease while the absorbent materials are deployed to contain and control the spill. Site work will resume when the spill kit is resupplied with a sufficient quantity of material capable of effectively immobilizing the volume of petroleum-based fluids contained in the largest tank present at the site. i. As required by law, all significant releases of hazardous materials, including oil will be reported immediately to the Governor's Office of Emergency Services Warning Center, (800) 852-7550.
GEN-4. General Site Disturbance Restrictions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Staging areas would be established in upland (rather than wetland) areas that do not provide habitat for federally-listed species; such staging areas would typically be located on bare ground, paved or graveled areas, ruderal habitat, or non-native grassland. b. All activity within vegetated marsh habitat would be minimized. c. For work occurring adjacent to wetlands, the limits of work will be clearly marked with brightly colored fencing or flagging. Silt fencing will be erected along the project boundaries adjacent to wetlands or other sensitive habitats. d. Stockpiled soils will be located away from the Bayfront Canal and adjacent sensitive habitats and a straw wattle or other erosion control material will surround the stockpile until it is disposed of or used. e. Access to the project site will be via existing roads and access ramps. f. The County will conduct weekly inspections of the site to ensure contractors have not gone beyond the limits of work. If the contractor has gone beyond the limits of work, the County will re-establish the fencing and conduct immediate restoration of any damage to sensitive habitats outside the work limits in consultation with the California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW) and Service.
GEN-5. Erosion Control Measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Protect storm drain inlets, gutters, ditches, and drainage courses with appropriate BMPs, such as gravel bags, fiber rolls, berms, etc. b. Prevent sediment from migrating off-site by installing and

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
	<p>maintaining sediment controls, such as fiber rolls, silt fences, or sediment basins. Erosion control fabrics will be constructed of biodegradable materials such as coir or jute, unless otherwise authorized by CDFW.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> c. A supply of emergency erosion control materials will be on hand at the project site. d. Keep excavated soil on the site where it will not collect into the street or adjacent sensitive habitats. e. Transfer excavated materials to dump trucks on the site, not in the street, as feasible. f. Cover haul trucks transporting soil, sand, or other loose materials off-site. g. All exposed soils within the work area will be stabilized immediately following the completion of earthmoving activities to prevent erosion into adjacent wetlands and channels. h. The County will monitor the above-described sediment and erosion control BMPs during and after each storm event for effectiveness. Modifications, repairs and improvements to these BMPs will be made as needed to protect water quality.
GEN-6. Dust Control	<p>The County will implement the Bay Area Air Quality Management District (BAAQMD) Basic Dust Control Measures. Current measures stipulated by the BAAQMD Guidelines include the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. All exposed surfaces (e.g., parking areas, staging areas, soil piles, graded areas, and unpaved access roads) shall be watered at least two times per day, and more often during periods of high wind. b. All haul trucks transporting soil, sand, or other loose material off-site shall be covered. c. All visible mud or dirt track-out onto adjacent public roads shall be removed using wet power vacuum street sweepers at least once per day. The use of dry power sweeping is prohibited. d. All vehicle speeds on unpaved roads shall be limited to 15 mph. e. All roadways, driveways, and sidewalks to be paved shall be completed as soon as possible. Building pads shall be laid as soon as possible after grading unless seeding or soil binders are used. f. Idling times shall be minimized either by shutting equipment off when not in use or reducing the maximum idling time to 5 minutes (as required by the California

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
	<p>airborne toxics control measure Title 13, Section 2485 of California Code of Regulations [CCR]). Clear signage shall be provided for construction workers at all access points.</p> <p>g. All construction equipment shall be maintained and properly tuned in accordance with manufacturer's specifications. All equipment shall be checked by a certified visible emissions evaluator.</p> <p>h. Post a publicly visible sign with the telephone number and person to contact at the County regarding dust complaints. Following the review of any dust complaints, the County project manager shall respond and take corrective action within 48 hours.</p>
GEN-7. Dewatering Requirements	<p>Prior to initiating construction of the diversion structure, the primary method for keeping water out of the work area will entail installation of sheet piles between the work area and the active Bayfront Canal channel. Clean gravel bags may be used to fill gaps or to extend barriers preventing flow from entering the work area. If needed, the diversion structure work space will be dewatered.</p> <p>a. During construction dewatering, treated water that is released back into Bayfront Canal or Flood Slough will be controlled such that the release rate doesn't increase turbidity to the receiving waters that could be deleterious to aquatic life.</p> <p>b. The County may discharge pumped water back into channel in accordance with conditions of the National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) Construction General Permit (State Water Resources Control Board Order No. 2009-0009-DWQ) and/or San Francisco Bay Region Municipal Regional Stormwater NPDES Permit. (Regional Water Quality Control Board (RWQCB) Order No. R2-2015-0049). Extracted water may also be discharged to upland areas nearby, such as to water plants/landscaping or contained and transported to a local wastewater treatment facility for treatment. Water collected and contained will be disposed of according to federal, state, and local regulations.</p> <p>c. When construction is completed, sheet piling, gravel bags, and silt fences will be removed as soon as possible. Impounded water will be released at a reduced velocity to minimize erosion, turbidity, or harm to aquatic life.</p>
GEN-8. Sand Bags/Rock Socks	Sandbags may be used during construction to form dewatered areas such as cofferdams or clean water bypasses. Sandbags

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
	<p>placed around drainage inlets divert flow away from the inlet. Rock socks may be used to protect inlets by providing filtration of runoff while allowing flow to enter the storm drain system.</p> <p>Construction Guidelines:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> If used along the Bayfront Canal, this BMP must be used in accordance with permit conditions. Secure ends of sandbags to ensure material does not scatter. When used as a barrier, stack bags tightly together and in alternative (brick-layer) fashion. <p>BMP Maintenance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> During construction, inspect daily during the work week. Schedule additional inspections during storm events. Make any required repairs. Replace damaged sandbags/rock socks. Remove sediment when deposits reach $\frac{1}{2}$ the height of the sandbag barrier. Replace rock socks when $\frac{1}{2}$ full of sediment or when water no longer flows through rock sock or when water is not clean after flowing through rock sock.
GEN-9. Hazardous Materials	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Label all hazardous materials and hazardous wastes (such as pesticides, paints, thinners, solvents, fuel, oil, and antifreeze) in accordance with city, county, state, and federal regulations. Store hazardous materials and wastes in water tight containers, store in appropriate secondary containment, and cover them at the end of every work day or during wet weather or when rain is forecast. Follow manufacturer's application instructions for hazardous materials and be careful not to use more than necessary. Do not apply chemicals outdoors when rain is forecast within 24 hours. Arrange for appropriate disposal of all hazardous wastes.
GEN-10. Waste Management	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Cover waste disposal containers securely with tarps at the end of every work day and during wet weather. No construction debris or waste will be allowed to enter adjacent channels, wetlands, or environmentally sensitive areas. Check waste disposal containers frequently for leaks and to make sure they are not overfilled. Never hose down a dumpster on the construction site. Clean or replace portable toilets, and inspect them frequently for leaks and spills. Dispose all wastes and debris properly. Recycle materials

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
	<p>and wastes that can be recycled (such as asphalt, concrete, aggregate base materials, wood, gyp board, pipe, etc.)</p> <p>f. Dispose of liquid residues from paints, thinners, solvents, glues, and cleaning fluids as hazardous waste.</p> <p>g. All temporary fences, barriers, and/or flagging will be completely removed from work sites and properly disposed of upon completion of construction activities.</p>
GEN-11. Concrete, Grout & Mortar Application	<p>a. Install the necessary containment structures to control the placement of wet concrete and to prevent it from entering into drainage channels outside of those structures. No concrete will be poured within the high flow line if the 15-day weather forecast indicates any chance of rain.</p> <p>b. When working with wet concrete, a monitor will be onsite to inspect the containment structures and ensure that no concrete or debris enters into the Bayfront Canal outside of those structures. Runoff from the concrete will not be allowed to enter the Bayfront Canal at any time.</p> <p>c. If feasible, poured concrete will be excluded from the wetted Bayfront Canal channel for a period of 30 days after it is poured. During that time, the poured concrete will be kept moist, and runoff from the concrete will not be allowed to enter a live stream. If the 30-day period is infeasible, the County will institute a minimum 3-day curing period and apply a non-toxic sealant designed for use in aquatic environments. The sealant will be allowed to cure for a minimum of 72 hours and until the sealant is dry.</p> <p>d. If rain occurs after pouring or concrete cannot be excluded from the wetted channel for a period of 30 days, the County will monitor the pH of any water that has come into contact with the poured concrete. If the water has a pH of 9.0 or greater, the water will be pumped to a tanker truck or to a lined off-channel basin and allowed to evaporate or be transported to an appropriate facility for disposal. During the pH monitoring period, all water that has come in contact with poured concrete will be isolated and not allowed to enter the water or otherwise come in contact with fish and other aquatic resources. The water will be retested until pH values become less than 9.0.</p> <p>e. Store concrete, grout, and mortar under cover, on pallets, and away from drainage areas. These materials must never reach a storm drain.</p> <p>f. Wash out concrete equipment/trucks off-site or in a contained area, so there is no discharge into the underlying</p>

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
	<p>soil or onto surrounding areas. Let concrete harden and dispose of as garbage.</p> <p>g. Collect the wash water from washing exposed aggregate concrete and remove it for appropriate disposal off-site.</p>
<i>Work Windows and Biological Avoidance and Minimization Measures for Project Activities</i>	
BIO-1. Work in Waters	<p>a. Work within perennial waters shall be performed only between June 15 and October 15 to minimize adverse impacts to wildlife and their habitats.</p> <p>b. Construction activities occurring below the High Tide Line or Ordinary High Water of Bayfront Canal will take place during the low-flow period and between May 1 and October 15. Exceptions may be made for this project with advance approval of the RWQCB, CDFW, National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), and/or Service as appropriate.</p> <p>c. Equipment shall not be operated in wetted areas (including but not limited to ponded, flowing, or wetland areas) or within the channel below the level of top-of-bank. No equipment shall be operated in a live stream channel.</p>
BIO-2. Environmental Awareness Training	<p>a. All project personnel will participate in a worker environmental awareness training program. Under this program, Project personnel will be informed about the presence of listed species (e.g., western snowy plover, California least tern, California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, longfin smelt, Central California Coast steelhead, and green sturgeon) and habitats associated with the species and that unlawful take of the animal or destruction of its habitat is a violation of the Federal and State Endangered Species Acts. Prior to project construction activities, a qualified biologist approved by CDFW, Service, and NMFS will instruct all project personnel about: (1) the description and status of the species; (2) the importance of their associated habitats; and (3) a list of measures being taken to reduce impacts on these species during project construction. A fact sheet conveying this information will be prepared for distribution to the project crew and anyone else who enters the project site.</p> <p>b. A member of the project crew will be designated as the point of contact for any employee or contractor who might inadvertently kill or injure a listed species or who finds a dead, injured, or entrapped listed species. The representative's name and telephone number will be provided to CDFW, Service, and NMFS prior to the</p>

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
	initiation of any activities.
BIO-3. Protection of Nesting Birds	<p>For construction activities involving heavy equipment, ground disturbance, or vegetation removal that are scheduled during the nesting season (March 15 to August 31 for smaller bird species such as passerines; February 15 to September 15 for raptors), a focused survey for active bird nests shall be conducted by a qualified biologist within 7 days prior to the beginning of Project activities. The minimum survey radii surrounding the work area shall be the following: i) 250 feet for passerines; ii) 500 feet for small raptors such as accipiters, iii) 1,000 feet for larger raptors such as buteos. If active nests are found, the County shall consult with the CDFW and Service regarding appropriate action to comply with the Migratory Bird Treaty Act of 1918 and the Fish & Game Code, section 3503.</p> <p>Active nests shall be designated as “Ecologically Sensitive Areas” and protected (while occupied) during construction activities with the establishment of temporary construction fencing, barriers, and/or flagging surrounding the nest site. The typical minimum distances of the protective buffers surrounding each identified nest site is usually the following: i) 1,000 feet for large raptors such as buteos; ii) 250 feet for small raptors such as accipiters; iii) 250 feet for passerines. A biological monitor shall monitor the behavior of the birds (adults and young, when present) at the nest site to ensure that they are not disturbed by project-related activities. Nest monitoring shall continue during project-related construction work until the young have fully fledged, are no longer being fed by the parents and have left the nest site, as determined by the approved biological monitor.</p>
BIO-4. Protection of Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. All vegetation within potential habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse within the project site and within a 2-foot buffer around the project footprint shall be removed by hand using only nonmechanized hand tools (i.e., trowel, hoe, rake, and shovel) prior to the initiation of work within these areas. Pickleweed stands will be removed by hand or weedwhacker. Vegetation shall be removed to bare ground or stubble no higher than 1 inch. Vegetation shall be removed under the supervision of a Service-approved biologist. Vegetation removal may begin when no mice are observed and shall start at the edge farthest from the salt marsh or the poorest habitat and work its way towards better salt marsh habitat, and from center of project outward. b. Silt fences would be erected adjacent to construction areas to define and isolate potential mouse habitat.

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
	<p>c. Temporary exclusion fencing shall be installed immediately after the hand removal of all vegetation (as described above) from the work area and a 2-foot buffer around the work area. The fence shall be made of a heavy plastic sheeting material that does not allow salt marsh harvest mice to pass through or climb, and the bottom shall be buried to a depth of 4 inches so that salt marsh harvest mouse cannot crawl under the fence. Fence height shall be at least 12 inches higher than the highest adjacent vegetation with a maximum height of 4 feet. All supports for the exclusion fencing shall be placed on the inside of the work area. The Service-approved biologist will have the ability to make field adjustments to the location of the fencing depending on site-specific habitat conditions.</p> <p>d. Prior to the initiation of work each day, the person(s) designated by the Service-approved biologist shall thoroughly inspect the work area and adjacent habitat areas to determine if salt marsh harvest mouse is present. Any necessary repairs to the exclusion fencing shall be completed within 24 hours of the initial observance of the damage. Work shall not continue within 300 feet of the damaged exclusion fencing until the fences are repaired. In the event salt marsh harvest mice have entered the work area, the Service-approved biologist would contact the Refuge and the Refuge would relocate the mice prior to the start of construction in the project site.</p> <p>e. No work will occur within 50 feet of suitable tidal marsh habitat within two hours before and after an extreme high tide event (6.5 feet or higher measured at the Golden Gate Bridge and adjusted to the timing of local high tides) unless salt marsh harvest mouse- proof exclusion fencing has been installed around the work area.</p> <p>f. Anyone accessing salt marsh harvest mouse habitat will walk carefully through the marsh, avoiding high pickleweed cover and wrack where harvest mice are likely to nest or find cover.</p>
BIO-5. Protection of California Clapper Rail	<p>a. Unless otherwise authorized by the Service and CDFW, operation of construction equipment and other construction, maintenance or monitoring activities within or adjacent to tidal marsh areas would be avoided to the maximum extent practicable during the California clapper rail breeding season from February 1 through August 31. If project activities occur during rail breeding season, surveys may be conducted to determine if rail locations</p>

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
	<p>and rail territories can be avoided, or if the marsh is determined to be unsuitable rail breeding habitat by a qualified biologist.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> b. Temporary perimeter fencing will be installed along the periphery of Flood Slough to isolate the slough from areas of active construction. c. Presence/absence of California clapper rail adjacent to the project area at Flood Slough will be based on data collected by the Invasive Spartina Project, which conducts annual breeding season surveys in Flood Slough. d. If the surveys confirm there are no breeding rails within 700 feet of the project limits adjoining Flood Slough, work can occur unimpeded from June 1 to October 31. e. If California clapper rails are present in the immediate construction area, the following measures would apply during construction activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To minimize or avoid the loss of individual California clapper rails, activities within or adjacent to California clapper rail habitat would not occur within 2 hours before or after extreme high tides (6.5 feet or above, as measured at the Golden Gate Bridge), when the marsh plain is inundated, because protective cover for California clapper rails is limited and activities could prevent them from reaching available cover. 2. If breeding California clapper rails are determined to be present, activities would not occur within 700 feet of an identified calling center. If the intervening distance across a major slough channel or across a substantial barrier between the California clapper rail calling center and any activity area is greater than 200 feet, it may proceed at that location within the breeding season. 3. If a California clapper rail nest is encountered during any project-related activity, the observers would immediately leave the vicinity of the nest; and if rail adults are encountered, observers would move away from the birds if they are giving alarm calls or otherwise appear alarmed. 4. Construction is anticipated to be initiated prior to the California clapper rail breeding season. Should there be construction delays greater than 3 days during the California clapper rail breeding season or should construction be initiated during the California clapper rail breeding season, sound-attenuating blankets will

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
	be installed on the perimeter fencing between the project and suitable habitat for California clapper rail habitat in Flood Slough. Installation of the sound-attenuating blankets will reduce noise traveling to adjacent habitat areas.
BIO-6. Protection of Western Snowy Plover	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. To the extent practicable, no construction, inspection, or maintenance activities would be performed within 600 feet of an active western snowy plover nest during the western snowy plover breeding season (March 1 through September 14, or as determined through surveys) without the approval of the Service. b. If chicks are present and are foraging along any levee that would be accessed by vehicles (e.g., for construction, inspection, or access), a qualified biologist would be present to ensure that no chicks are present within the path of the vehicle.
BIO-7. Protection of California Least Tern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. To the extent practicable, no construction, inspection, or maintenance activities would be performed within 300 feet of an active least tern nest during the least tern breeding season (April 15 to August 15, or as determined through surveys) without the approval of the Service.
BIO-8. Protection of Listed Fish Species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Sheet piling would be placed in the Bayfront Canal during low tide to keep fish and aquatic life out of the construction area. Sheet piling would be installed just prior to the beginning of the construction and removed promptly after completion so that the period of dewatering is minimized. b. A "soft start" technique will be implemented during sheet pile installation activities to reduce hydroacoustic effects on native fish and potentially allow for any federally or state-listed fish species in the vicinity work area to leave c. Hydroacoustic effects will be minimized to exposure thresholds for which injury or mortality of fish is not anticipated. The NMFS Pile Driving Calculator will be used to estimate the potential underwater noise-related effects on fish species for construction. An iterative approach would be used to determine the number of pile strikes that could be made within a 12-hour period without surpassing the peak sound pressure level (peak) and cumulative sound exposure level (SEL) thresholds established in the Technical Guidance for Assessment and Mitigation of Hydroacoustic Effects of Pile Driving on Fish (ICF Jones & Stokes and Illingworth and Rodkin 2009 as cited in Horizon Water and Environment 2020).

Table 3. Conservation Measures	
Measure Title or Topic	Description
	Pile driving with an impact hammer shall be limited to the number of strikes per 12 hours that is below the peak and cumulative SEL thresholds. The number of strikes shall be recorded by a NMFS/Service-approved monitor and reported to NMFS and Service on request or in a post-construction compliance report.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” The Action Area for this consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the project and the broader area that, while outside the Project footprint, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, dust, light, or movement associated with the proposed project. Specifically, the Action Area includes: Marsh Road, the Bayfront Canal, south of the Flood Slough tide gates, to the Pond S5 Forebay and a 300-foot buffer defined in the biological assessment to account for construction-related noise (a noise impact analysis was not conducted). The biological assessment stated the operations and maintenance of the project would not result in an expansion of the geographic extent of effects beyond the Action Area it defined for construction, but operations are in conjunction with tide gate operations for the SBSP Restoration Project. The biological assessment mapped the Action Area but did not quantify the acreage; therefore, the Service estimates the total Action Area to be approximately 55 acres.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status

of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of the Species

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. The Service is in the process of developing our current 5-year review for the species.

California Clapper Rail

Information about the California clapper rail biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the California clapper rail 5-year Review, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc6592.pdf (Service 2020). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The Environmental Baseline includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

Parcels in the Action Area are owned by Cargill Salt, West Bay Sanitary District, the City of Redwood City, and the City of Menlo Park. The Action Area is generally bound by Haven Avenue and Bayfront Expressway to the south, Flood Slough and Bedwell Bayfront Park to the north, the Cargill Industrial Saltworks to the west, and the SBSR Restoration Ravenswood Pond Complex to the east. Existing land uses in the vicinity are comprised of business parks,

recreational open space and restored wetlands, and industrial uses. The Bayfront Expressway, located immediately south of the project, generates considerable noise and there are also high levels of adjacent human disturbance.

The Action Area is located in historic baylands. Bayfront Canal, located in the western portion of the Action Area, receives runoff from Redwood City and Menlo Park. Bayfront Canal also receives runoff from the Town of Atherton, City of Woodside, and unincorporated San Mateo County that is conveyed to the Bayfront Canal via the Atherton Channel, approximately 500 feet west of the Project Area. Atherton Channel is the primary runoff source and contributes approximately 38 percent of the Bayfront Canal's total flow. The Bayfront Canal merges with the Atherton Channel near Marsh Road and then outlets into Flood Slough through a tide control structure maintained and operated by the City of Redwood City. A canal located in the southern portion of the Project Area is within the Caltrans right-of-way, known as the Caltrans stormwater channel. This channel drains to Flood Slough. The Pond S5 Forebay, a former salt pond, is within the Action Area. Small depressional areas and conveyance channels formally used for salt production brine transfer are also present.

Open Water

Open water habitat includes former salt production ponds and brine conveyance channels, the Bayfront Canal, the Caltrans stormwater channel, and depressions. The Action Area includes the Pond S5 Forebay, which was used as a salt production pond in the past. During an April 2018 site visit, the pond was observed to be mostly dry, with open water present in deeper portions of the pond along the ponds northern and southern perimeter. This pond is part of a larger pond complex that is currently managed for waterbirds by the SBSP Restoration Project.

Brackish Marsh

Small bands of brackish marsh (varying between 1 and 10 feet in width) line the nontidal channels and ponds in the Action Area. Dominant species in these areas include pickleweed (*Salicornia* sp.), salt grass (*Distichlis spicata*) and alkali heath (*Frankenia salina*). These brackish marsh habitats contain salt-adapted species due to the project location on fill over bay mud and/or potential saline groundwater interception from the bay, which can create saline or alkaline conditions (H.T. Harvey 2017 as cited in Horizon Water and Environment 2020).

Tidal Marsh

Flood Slough is open to tidal influence, and contains tidal marsh dominated by pickleweed and alkali heath, with gumplant (*Grindelia stricta*) also present.

Upland/Levee

Uplands and levees in the Action Area are dominated by ruderal species. These include wild oats (*Avena* spp.), ripgut brome (*Bromus diandrus*), Italian rye grass (*Festuca perennis*), tall wheat grass (*Elymus ponticus*), Mediterranean barley (*Hordeum marinum* ssp. *gussoneanum*), common mallow (*Malva neglecta*), and fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*).

Developed/Disturbed

Portions of the Action Area are characterized as a developed/disturbed habitat. These include Marsh Road, adjacent parking areas, and the pump station.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Salt marsh harvest mice are known to occur along Flood Slough (CDFW 2017 as cited in Horizon Water and Environment 2020; Shellhammer 2005 as cited in Horizon Water and Environment 2020), and tidal salt marsh habitat in Flood Slough within the Action Area provides suitable habitat for this species. Narrow strips of brackish marsh dominated by salt marsh plant species occur along the edges of ponds and channels in the Action Area and provide low-quality habitat for salt marsh harvest mouse, but this species may potentially occasionally disperse through these areas (H.T. Harvey 2017 as cited in Horizon Water and Environment 2020) while traveling between areas of high quality salt marsh habitat.

California Clapper Rail

The California clapper rail is known to occur in Flood Slough (a portion of which is within the Action Area), as well as in Greco Island, north of the Action Area (CDFW 2018 as cited in Horizon Water and Environment 2020). The Invasive Spartina Project has conducted annual surveys since 2006 along Flood Slough during the California clapper rail breeding season, and these surveys detected clapper rails in the Action Area in 2018 and 2019 (McBroom 2018 as cited in Horizon Water and Environment 2020; Olofson Environmental 2020). Additionally, a passive survey completed by H.T. Harvey in January of 2020 detected California clapper rails approximately 650 feet north of the project area in Flood Slough (Horizon Water and Environment 2020). There is no suitable habitat for the California clapper rail in the construction footprint.

Biological Opinions within the Action Area

The Service issued a programmatic biological opinion for the 50-year SBSP Restoration Project on August 12, 2008 and a tiered biological opinion for Phase 1 (Service file no. 81420-08-F-0621). The Service issued a tiered biological opinion from the 2008 programmatic biological opinion for the first part of Phase 2 of the SBSP Restoration Project on November 21, 2017 (Service file no. 08FBDT00-2017-F-0109-2). Phase 2 of the SBSP Restoration within the Ravenswood Pond Complex is underway, and construction is expected to extend beyond the timeline for this currently proposed project. Phase 2 includes water control structures in the Action Area and the Pond S5 Forebay will be subject to new operations for wildlife enhancement by the Refuge.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the

proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the Action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

California Clapper Rail

No physical effects to habitat will occur as a result of the project. However, effects to individual California clapper rails will occur during construction. Visual disturbance from construction and noise impacts from pile driving could affect rails in an estimated 2.6 acres of tidal marsh in Flood Slough. Equipment noise and vibration may interfere with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. The project is expected to have 4 distinct episodes of pile driving activity, each of which will occur for no more than a few hours per day over a 2 to 3-day period.

Due to the detection of a California Clapper rail approximately 650 feet north of the construction footprint in Flood Slough in January 2020, additional measures will be followed to avoid adverse effects to this species should rail breeding occur within Flood Slough. These measures, mentioned above, include initiating a continuous construction process outside of the California clapper rail breeding season, installing sheet pile cofferdams outside of the breeding season to minimize construction noise impacts during the breeding season, and installation of sound-attenuation blankets on temporary periphery fencing if there will be a construction delay of 3 days or greater during the rail breeding season. In addition to reducing noise from project construction, the sound-attenuating blankets will reduce visual impacts of project construction on California clapper rail. Although a noise analysis was not conducted, full implementation of these measures should reduce or eliminate potential disturbance to rails nesting in Flood Slough.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The proposed project will generate temporary noise and visual disturbance that will exceed ambient conditions in areas that may support salt marsh harvest mice. Equipment noise and vibration may interfere with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Intolerable levels of disturbance that may force individual mice to flush from cover or prevent them from seeking available cover could expose them to a predation risk that otherwise would not occur. Implementation of Avoidance and Minimization Measure BIO-4 will minimize the potential for construction-related adverse effects on salt marsh harvest mouse. However, capturing and relocating mice could result in injury or mortality of individuals.

The proposed project will disturb up to 0.22 acre of marginally suitable dispersal habitat, through dredging and or filling, including approximately 0.19 acre of permanent impacts. These areas are narrow and are not likely to support individual salt marsh harvest mice. Berm lowering would result in permanent impacts to 0.28 acre of upland habitat adjacent to marginally suitable dispersal habitat, through grading of the habitat to a lower elevation that would transition this area from upland vegetation to brackish marsh vegetation. Over time, berm lowering is anticipated to result in the onsite restoration of 0.28 acre of suitable dispersal habitat (from upland vegetation to brackish/salt marsh) for the salt marsh harvest mouse.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative Effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species* for the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail, the *Environmental Baseline* for the Action Area, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that the proposed project is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the salt marsh harvest mouse or California clapper rail. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the *Environmental Baseline* and analyzed in consideration of all potential *Cumulative Effects*, will not rise to the level of reducing the likelihood of survival or recovery of the species based on the following: (1) construction effects like noise disturbance will be temporary; (2) no physical disturbance to California clapper rail habitat will occur; and (3) only marginal habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse will be subject to physical disturbance and 0.28 acre of salt marsh habitat will be restored onsite.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by Service regulations at 50 CFR § 17.3 as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to a listed species by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavioral patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding or sheltering. Harm is defined by the same regulations as an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Harm is further defined to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act, provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the Applicants, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions, or (2) fails to require the (Applicants) to adhere to the

terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR § 402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

California Clapper Rail

The Service anticipates incidental take of the California clapper rail will be difficult to detect or quantify because of their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy of vegetation types resulting in low detectability. The Service anticipates take incidental to the proposed action in the form of harm, by impairing essential behaviors such as breeding, foraging, or predator evasion, of all California clapper rails in the salt and brackish marsh habitat adjacent to the construction areas within the approximately 55-acre Action Area. Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of California clapper rails associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The Service anticipates incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse will be difficult to detect or quantify because of their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy of vegetation types resulting in low detectability. There is a risk of injury or mortality as a result of the proposed activities and subsequent temporary loss or degradation of suitable habitat. Therefore, the Service anticipates take incidental to the proposed action in the form of injury, or mortality of all salt marsh harvest mice within the approximately 55-acre Action Area subject to habitat modification and capture and relocation and in the form of harm, by impairing essential behaviors such as breeding, foraging, or predator evasion, of all salt marsh harvest mice in the salt and brackish marsh habitat adjacent to the construction areas within the approximately 55-acre Action Area. Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of salt marsh harvest mice associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that the level of anticipated take is not likely to jeopardize the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail resulting from implementation of this project have been

incorporated into the project's proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail:

1. The Corps through the applicant and its contractors will minimize the potential incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure compliance with the following term and conditions, which implement the reasonable and prudent measure described above. This Term and Condition is non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - a. At least 15 days prior to the proposed project implementation, the Corps and/or the applicant will submit to the Service, for approval, the name(s) and credentials of biologists it requests to be biological monitors specified for this proposed project. Information included in a request for authorization must include, at a minimum: (1) relevant education; (2) relevant training on species identification, survey techniques, handling individuals of different age classes, and handling of different life stages by a permitted biologist or recognized species expert authorized for such activities by the Service; (3) a summary of field experience conducting requested activities (to include project/research information and actual experience with the species); (4) a summary of biological opinions and/or informal consultations under which they were authorized to work with the listed species and at what level (such as construction monitoring versus handling), this should also include the names and qualifications of persons under which the work was supervised as well as the amount of work experience on the actual project including detail on whether the species was encountered or not; and (5) a list of 10(a)(1)(A) permits, if any, held or under which individuals are authorized to work with the species (to include permit number, authorized activities, and name of permit holder).
 - b. The Corps shall minimize the potential for harm, killing or other forms of take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail from project-related activities by implementation of the *Conservation Measures* proposed in the *Description of the Proposed Action* in this biological opinion.
 - c. The Corps shall ensure that their applicant immediately notifies the Service of any killed, injured, or entrapped salt marsh harvest mice or California clapper rail, within one (1) working day of the detection. Please contact the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-2664.

- d. The Corps and/or their applicant shall educate and inform personnel involved in the project as to the *Conservation Measures* and *Terms and Conditions* in this biological opinion.
- e. The Corps shall comply with the reporting requirements of this biological opinion, including a post-construction report outlining how the *Conservation Measures* were implemented for this project.
- f. The Corps and/or their applicant shall ensure any personnel identified as biological monitors or biologists, who are responsible for ensuring compliance with the *Conservation Measures* or other parts of the project which may affect federally-listed species, be Service-approved prior to implementing those activities.
- g. The Corps and/or their applicant shall provide a salt marsh harvest relocation plan to the Refuge and the Service's San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office for review and approval.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the Project is approached or exceeded, the Corps shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR § 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed Project. Injured listed species shall be cared by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person, such as the Service-approved biologist for the proposed Project. Notification will be made to the contact above in Term and Condition 1c, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken section below.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and the California Natural Diversity Data Base (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/CNDDDB/Submitting-Data>).
3. The Corps' applicant shall submit a post-construction compliance report prepared by the on-site biologist to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office within 60 calendar days of the date of the completion of construction activities. This report shall detail (i) dates that construction occurred; (ii) pertinent information concerning the success of the Project in meeting the avoidance and minimization measures; (iii) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (iv) known project effects on the salt

marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail, if any; (v) occurrences of incidental take of these listed species, if any; (vi) documentation of employee environmental education; and (vii) other pertinent information.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact persons are the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

- 1) Encourage or require the use of appropriate California native species in restoration efforts.
- 2) Facilitate additional educational programs geared toward the importance and conservation of tidal marsh and seasonal wetlands.
- 3) Assist the Service with implementing other recovery actions identified within the most current recovery plans for salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes consultation for the Bayfront Canal and Atherton Channel Flood Management and Restoration Project. As provided in 50 CFR § 402.16,

- 1) Reinitiation of formal consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service where discretionary Federal agency involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:

- A) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
 - B) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
 - C) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion; or
 - D) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.
- 2) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:
- A) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
 - B) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

If you have any questions regarding this biological opinion, please contact Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager (Kim_Squires@fws.gov), at the letterhead address, or at 916-930-5634. Please reference the Service File Number 08FBDT00-2020-F-0020 in any correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

(Acting)

Kaylee Allen
Field Supervisor

LITERATURE CITED

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